

Supplementary

A. Regression analysis data for the assay calibration curves for NSAIDs studied

In purified water				
Drug	n	r	s	best fit equation
Biphenylacetic Acid	6	0.992	0.071	$A = 0.105 + 0.027 C$
Diclofenac	6	0.992	0.015	$A = 0.021 + 0.006 C$
Diclofenac Na	6	0.996	0.044	$A = 0.066 + 0.017 C$
Indomethacin	6	0.991	0.028	$A = 0.041 + 0.013 C$
Piroxicam	6	0.993	0.075	$A = 0.111 + 0.028 C$
In phosphate buffer (pH 7.4)				
Drug	n	r	s	best fit equation
Biphenylacetic Acid	6	0.999	0.014	$A = 0.004 + 0.021 C$
Diclofenac	6	1.000	0.021	$A = 0.018 + 0.039 C$
Diclofenac Na	6	1.000	0.012	$A = 0.003 + 0.029 C$
Indomethacin	6	0.992	0.094	$A = 0.141 + 0.036 C$
Piroxicam	6	0.991	0.101	$A = 0.147 + 0.038 C$
In <i>n</i> -octanol				
Drug	n	r	s	best fit equation
Biphenylacetic Acid	6	1.000	0.016	$A = 0.008 + 0.051 C$
Diclofenac	6	0.998	0.029	$A = 0.016 + 0.037 C$
Diclofenac Na	6	1.000	0.011	$A = 0.008 + 0.041 C$
Indomethacin	6	0.966	0.031	$A = 0.001 + 0.015 C$
Piroxicam	6	0.999	0.013	$A = 0.002 + 0.048 C$

where, n = number of observations, r = regression coefficient, s = standard error, A = absorbance, and C = concentration of the compound in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

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B. Determination of ionization constant (pK_a) for the NSAIDs studied [pK_a was calculated by: $pH + \text{column 5}$]

pK_a determination of biphenylacetic acid						pK_a determination of diclofenac					
pH	A	A - A _i	A _m - A	$\log \frac{A - A_i}{A_m - A}$	pK_a	pH	A	A - A _i	A _m - A	$\log \frac{A - A_i}{A_m - A}$	pK_a
4.75	0.602	0.213	1.313	-0.790	3.96	5.54	0.616	0.424	0.940	-0.346	5.19
4.55	0.725	0.336	1.190	-0.549	4.00	5.34	0.751	0.559	0.805	-0.158	5.18
4.35	0.842	0.453	1.073	-0.375	3.98	5.14	0.875	0.683	0.681	0.001	5.14
4.15	0.996	0.577	0.949	-0.216	3.93	4.94	1.015	0.823	0.541	0.182	5.12
3.95	1.205	0.816	0.710	0.060	4.01	4.74	1.112	0.920	0.444	0.316	5.06
3.75	1.325	0.936	0.590	0.200	3.95	4.54	1.237	1.045	0.319	0.515	5.06
3.55	1.445	1.056	0.470	0.352	3.90	4.34	1.343	1.151	0.213	0.733	5.07
pK_a determination of diclofenac sodium						pK_a determination of indomethacin					
pH	A	A - A _i	A _m - A	$\log \frac{A - A_i}{A_m - A}$	pK_a	pH	A	A - A _i	A _m - A	$\log \frac{A - A_i}{A_m - A}$	pK_a
5.97	0.898	0.669	0.831	-0.090	5.84	5.41	0.310	0.141	0.782	-0.744	4.67
5.77	1.014	0.785	0.715	0.410	5.77	5.21	0.383	0.211	0.712	-0.528	4.68
5.57	1.111	0.882	0.618	0.155	5.96	5.01	0.461	0.289	0.634	-0.341	4.67
5.37	1.293	1.064	0.436	0.369	5.70	4.81	0.523	0.351	0.572	-0.212	4.60
5.13	1.410	1.181	0.319	0.569	5.70	4.61	0.637	0.465	0.458	0.007	4.62
4.97	1.489	1.260	0.240	0.720	5.65	4.41	0.759	0.567	0.336	0.242	4.65
4.73	1.553	1.324	0.176	0.876	5.61	4.21	0.871	0.699	0.224	0.494	4.70
pK_a determination of diclofenac sodium						pK_a values (mean \pm SD, at 21°C)					
pH	A	A - A _i	A _m - A	$\log \frac{A - A_i}{A_m - A}$	pK_a						
4.84	0.727	0.038	0.258	-0.831	6.01	Biphenylacetic acid		3.96 \pm 0.04			
6.64	0.753	0.064	0.232	-0.559	6.08	Diclofenac		5.12 \pm 0.06			
6.44	0.787	0.098	0.198	-0.305	6.14	Diclofenac sodium		5.71 \pm 0.08			
6.24	0.821	0.132	0.164	-0.094	6.15	Indomethacin		4.66 \pm 0.04			
6.04	0.851	0.162	0.134	0.082	6.12	Piroxicam		6.11 \pm 0.05			
5.84	0.886	0.197	0.099	0.299	6.14						
5.64	0.912	0.223	0.073	0.485	6.13						

C. Preparation of diclofenac base

Diclofenac was prepared from diclofenac sodium as follows: diclofenac sodium was dissolved in the minimum amount of methanol (i.e. 1 in 10 ml) in a 50-ml beaker and about 5 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added followed by the addition of 40 ml of purified water and was transferred to a 1000-ml separating funnel. The beaker was then washed with 2 x 20 ml of purified water and added to the separating funnel to bring the volume of water to 80 ml. finally, 2 x 50 ml of ether was added to

the separating funnel. This system was well shaken for 10 minutes and allowed to separate into two phases, the ether phase on the top containing the base and the water phase being on the bottom containing the sodium. The lower phase was discarded and the upper phase was transferred into a flask. The ether phase in the flask was dried with magnesium sulfate (MgSO₄) overnight at room temperature. The ether was then evaporated using a rotary evaporator, and diclofenac was then collected. In order to confirm the conversion of diclofenac sodium to

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diclofenac base, further comparison of structural analysis on both agents was carried out by infra-red (IR) spectroscopy and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR).

Diclofenac sodium spectrum (**Fig. 1 B**) showed principle peaks at wavenumbers 3378, 3258 and 1576, 1557 cm^{-1} frequencies for NH and CO stretching, respectively. Both peaks showed clearly a split due to the effect of the sodium metal that is present in this compound. However, in the case of diclofenac base (**Fig. 1 A**), the IR spectroscopy showed that the NH stretching frequency at 3323 cm^{-1} and the CO stretching frequency at 1695 cm^{-1} as single sharp peaks with no splitting, indicating that no sodium is present in the compound. In addition, a broad peak at 2692 cm^{-1} frequency is seen in the spectrum which is assigned for the OH stretching. The IR spectra indicate that the ONa group was substituted by OH group.

In order to know whether the conversion of diclofenac sodium to diclofenac base has really occurred, further comparison of structural analysis on both drugs was

carried out by NMR (**Figure 2**). The results show that proton (1H) consists of a doublet $\delta 7.52$ ppm assigned to $\text{H}_{3,5}$ (2H), a triplet at $\delta 7.17$ ppm assigned to H_4 (1H), a doublet at $\delta 7.24$ ppm due to H_9 (1H), a triplet at $\delta 6.88$ ppm to H_{10} (1H), a triplet at $\delta 7.08$ ppm assigned to H_{11} (1H), a doublet $\delta 6.33$ ppm assigned to H_{12} (1H), and two singlets at $\delta 7.30$ ppm and $\delta 3.75$ ppm assigned to NH (1H) and CH_2 (1H), respectively.

The ^1H NMR spectrum for diclofenac base (**Fig. 2**) showed the aromatic protons as a doublet at $\delta 7.44$ ppm assigned to $\text{H}_{3,5}$ (2H), a triplet at $\delta 7.07$ ppm assigned to H_4 (1H), a doublet at $\delta 7.15$ ppm due to H_9 (1H), a triplet at $\delta 6.77$ ppm to H_{10} (1H), a triplet at $\delta 6.95$ ppm assigned to H_{11} (1H), a doublet $\delta 6.30$ ppm assigned to H_{12} (1H), and three singlets at $\delta 9.96$, $\delta 3.82$ and $\delta 3.75$ ppm and $\delta 3.75$ ppm assigned to NH (1H) and CH_2 (2H) and OH (1H), respectively. Therefore, diclofenac showed the presence of the OH signal.

Figure (1): IR spectra for diclofenac base (A) and diclofenac sodium (B).

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Diclofenac sodium

Diclofenac base

Figure (2): Proton NMR spectrum for diclofenac sodium and diclofenac base.